

BOLT BEARING BEHAVIOR OF HIGHLY LOADED COMPOSITE JOINTS AT ELEVATED TEMPERATURES WITH AND WITHOUT CLAMP-UP

Richard J. Wright¹, W. Steven Johnson², and Hafiz Ahmad³

*¹Mechanical Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology,
Atlanta, Georgia 30332-0405, USA*

*²Materials Science and Engineering, Georgia Institute of Technology,
Atlanta, Georgia 30332-0245, USA*

*³Lockheed Martin Aeronautical Systems, 86 South Cobb Drive, Zone 0648, Dept. 73-C2,
Marietta, GA 30063, USA*

SUMMARY: In this paper, data on time dependent behavior of bolted joints made from 64 ply IM7 carbon fiber/ K3B thermoplastic polyimide quasi-isotropic layup tested in pure bolt bearing and in bearing bypass is presented. Composite panels were aged at temperatures of 177°C (350°F) and 204°C (400°F) for 5000 and 10,000 hours to simulate cumulative effects of supersonic flight conditions on a bolted composite joint. Change in joint bearing capacity and determination of time dependent behavior have been covered in this study. For testing, coupons sized and drilled to correspond to the ratios found in actual joints were loaded to a wide range of loads both with and without clamp-up forces. Testing was done at a temperature of 177°C (350°F), to simulate supersonic cruise temperature. Bearing creep testing revealed time dependent behavior only in a very narrow loading region, above which bearing failure occurred almost instantaneously, and below which no damage occurred. Testing of aged material has shown degradation in material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5000 hours, however, material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 10,000 hours demonstrated a recovery in bearing capacity while comparison with material aged at 204°C (400°F) for 5000 and 10,000 hours showed neither equivalent nor increased performance degradation.

KEYWORDS: bolt, bearing, joints, creep, aging, bypass

INTRODUCTION

Aircraft traveling at supersonic speeds encounter increased skin temperatures as a result of aerodynamic friction. Future advanced high speed aircraft will be expected to sustain high speeds for longer periods of time than current aircraft can. At the same time, material advances have made composites very attractive for such an aircraft. Fatigue resistance and high strength to weight ratios suggest graphite fiber/thermoplastic composite systems as an alternative to metallic systems for primary structures in an advanced supersonic aircraft. Highly loaded bolted joints will be required in such structures. Since supersonic composite aircraft containing highly loaded bolted joints have never been produced, there is no existing database on how a composite system would perform over the life of a such an aircraft. Key issues about how such a joint would perform include actual strength of the joint under different loading conditions, effects of prolonged loading at cruise temperature, and degradation effects of long-term exposure to high temperatures.

The objective of this paper is to present data on the behavior of highly loaded bolted composite joints at elevated temperatures over long periods of time. The results of this research include data on observed bearing behavior and evaluation of thermal aging effects.

MATERIAL

The composite material being used for these tests is IM7 carbon fibers with K3B thermoplastic polyimide (manufactured by DuPont). Sixty- four ply quasi-isotropic ($[\pm 45^\circ/90^\circ/0^\circ]_4$) lay-up panels of material were fabricated by DuPont. Besides the panels left unaged for testing original properties, other panels were put into forced air aging ovens for aging at 177°C (350°F) and at 204°C (400°F). The aged panels were wrapped in fiberglass cloth to provide separation and cushioning without sacrificing surface exposure to airflow.

Coupons of material for testing were cut from the panels to correspond with an optimal bolt spacing as determined by experimental testing [1]. The ratio of coupon width to bolt hole diameter is six, and the ratio of edge distance to hole diameter is four as shown in Fig. 1. A slot for inserting a hole edge reference wire is cut into the bottom of the hole (on the grip side). The slot is sized to closely fit the measurement wire. The thickness of the coupon is the thickness of the panel. On average, specimens are .89cm (.35") thick.

EXPERIMENTAL SETUP

Configuration

The specific tests done in this program replicate the loading situation for a panel in pure bolt bearing. Pure bolt bearing as described here is a loading situation where 100% of the load in a panel is transmitted at the bolt hole. In a multi-row bolted joint, bolts along the edge of the panel are loaded in this condition. Single bolt holes at the edge of the panel in pure bolt bearing are modeled by a coupon with a bolt hole drilled through it. Bearing- bypass tests, where there is a load in the panel crossing the bolt hole as well as at the bolt hole were performed at Lockheed Martin.

Figure 1: Bolt bearing testing coupon geometry

The basic experimental test setup for the bolt bearing tests in Fig. 2 is similar to that used in past research [1] and consists of a clevis with a bushing in it to apply clamp-up force to the

coupon. A .95 cm (.374") diameter high strength steel aircraft bolt is put through the clevis and the coupon with the measurement wire hanging in the slot below the bolt hole.

Figure 2: Testing setup with clevis, specimen, extensometer, measurement wire, and grip.

On either side of the specimen, (in contact with its surface) are two 1.59cm (.625") diameter corrosion resistant steel aircraft washers .159cm (.0625i) thick, which are slotted to allow space for the measurement wire to pass. The coupon is held at the other end by a bolted grip with fine tungsten carbide teeth. Bolt hole elongation is measured with an MTS 2.54cm (1") gauge length clip-on extensometer mounted on the .16cm (.063") stainless steel wire with its free blade clip attached to a post on the clevis.

Testing

In bearing creep testing, the fixture is placed in an oven (temperature range for the ovens built for this testing is room temperature to 220°C (428°F)) with the coupon in place. A 20:1 lever arm creep machine supplies a static load for the duration of each test bearing creep test (250 hours). Output from the extensometer is routed through an analog amplifier and sent to a pen chart recorder so that hole displacement data is plotted as a function of time. One duplicate of each test was conducted.

EXPERIMENTAL RESULTS AND DISCUSSION

Bearing Creep

Bearing creep tests have all been run at 177°C (350°F). All specimens are dried for 62 days at 116°C (250°F) to remove any volatile content before being put in the creep frames for testing. Each test runs for a continuous 250 hours under load at temperature. Four basic series of bearing creep tests have been run: First, testing joints clamped up to 5.65 N·m (50 in-lb) torque with unaged coupons. Second, testing of unclamped bearing on unaged coupons where no washers or other constraint was present to prevent deformation of the specimens (washers were absent, but measurement wire was present). Third, testing of unclamped bearing on specimens aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5,000 and 10,000 hrs. Fourth, unclamped bearing testing on material aged at 204°C (400°F) for 5000 and 10,000 hrs. Loads for bearing creep are defined here in two ways: 1. Total load applied to the specimen (given in kN and lbs.). 2. Bearing load stress, which is defined by Eqn. (1) and is given in MPa and ksi. Data from these experiments given in Figures 3, 4, 5, and 6 is the average from each test and its duplicate. The very good reproducibility of the tests has put the runs very close to their duplicates.

$$\{\sigma_b\} = P/(t \cdot D) \quad (1)$$

Failure Criterion

Failure is defined as any permanent deformation of the bolt hole of 4% of its diameter or more (MIL-HDBK-5G, 1994), which is .038cm (.015”) in this instance. This failure criterion is illustrated here (as in Figure 4) as being the largest elastic deformation seen (immediately after loading in the 31.1 kN or 365.4 MPa (7000lbs. or 53ksi) test shown in Fig. 5) with the 4% of the diameter added to it.

Clamped-up Tests

These tests were done on unaged specimens with standard aircraft washers providing clamp up force on either side of the specimens. As seen in Fig. 3, the presence of clamp-up appears to have prevented bearing creep at loads up to 40 kN or 473 MPa (9000lbs. or 68.6 ksi), or 150% of the baseline load for the joint, 26.7kN or 315 MPa (6000 lbs. or 45.7 ksi). During testing, the washers on either side left marks on the specimens; these were found to be smoothed areas and not measurable indentions. The bolt holes in all of the test coupons recovered elastically to the original bolt hole diameter of .953cm (.375”).

Figure 3: Clamped-up Bolt Bearing Behavior of Unaged Material

Unclamped Bolt Bearing Tests

Based on the results of the clamped up specimens, the researchers decided to look at the worst case scenario for this joint system: Unclamped bearing, where the washers are removed from the bolt so that there is no constraining clamp-up to prevent spreading out of the material and failure of the laminate. In these tests, it was revealed that the laminate had sustained loads with clamp-up that would result in nearly instantaneous bearing failure without the constraining clamp-up force.

Unclamped Bolt Bearing In Unaged Material

The first series of unclamped bearing tests was carried out in unaged material. The coupons were dried before testing and slotted. The testing started at a load of 40kN or 473MPa (9000lbs. or 68.6ksi). This load produced rapid bearing failure, as can be seen in Figure 4. It appears that the critical value for sustaining loads is somewhere around 31.1 kN or 365.4 MPa (7000lbs. or 53ksi). At this load, the joint showed a creep-like failure pattern which moved until the material spread out enough to fill the clevis, thus producing the “Knee” visible in Figure 4. The damage to the specimen, however, appeared to be identical to the crushing and intralaminar cracking produced by outright bearing failure. Given the known properties of the matrix material in regard to brittleness increasing with temperature [3], this result is consistent. Note the absence of time dependent behavior in material at a slightly lower load of 28.9 kN or 341.5MPa (6500lbs. or 49.5ksi). Specimens tested at loads below 31.1 kN or 365.4 MPa (7000lbs. or 53ksi) recovered elastically to its original dimensions.

Figure 4: Unclamped Bearing Behavior of unaged material

Unclamped Bearing In Material Aged 5,000 and 10,000 Hours At 177°C (350°F)

The second series of unclamped bearing tests was performed with material which had been aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5,000 and 10,000 hours. In these tests, the target loads were the highest loads the unaged material had survived. As seen in Fig. 5, the material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5000 hours showed immediate bearing failure at 28.9 kN or 341MPa (6500 lbs. or 49.5 ksi). More interestingly, the material showed time dependent deformation that arrested itself at 26.7kN or 315 MPa (6000 lbs or 46.2 ksi). The specimens in the latter case had clear delaminations on either side above the bolt hole with the outer 45° plies pushed out from the specimen, creating bulges or ‘ears’. From these tests it is clear that there has been loss of unclamped bearing strength after aging at 177°C (350°F). At the same time, the damage remained bearing failure with delamination, crushing under the bolt, and outer ply separation. However, material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 10,000 hours appears to have shown a recovery in properties by sustaining a load of at 28.9 kN or 341MPa (6500 lbs. or 49.5 ksi) without damage and sustaining a load of 31.1 kN or 365.4 MPa (7000lbs. or 53ksi) for 2.3 hours before failure.

Figure 5: Unclamped Bearing Behavior of Material Age at 177°C (350°F)

Unclamped Bearing In Material Aged At 204°C (400°F)

Unclamped bearing tests were conducted with material aged for 5000 and 10,000 hours at 204°C (400°F). As in the last test, the strategy was to use the highest load the previous test had survived. For this test, the load was 26.7kN or 315 MPa (6000lbs. or 45.7ksi). The

Figure 6: Unclamped Bearing Behavior of Material Aged at 204°C (400°F)

unexpected result was that the material apparently was less affected by exposure to temperatures of 204°C (400°F) than it was when aged at 177°C (350°F). As can be seen in Figure 6, the material aged at this temperature did not show deformation at 26.7kN or 315 MPa (6000lbs. or 45.7ksi) the way material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5000 hours had. The specimen aged at 204°C (400°F) recovered elastically to its original dimensions. In comparison, the coupons aged at 177°C (350°F) tested at this same load both showed significant “Ears” on either side above the bolt hole where delamination had begun and apparently arrested when enough crushed material gathered to distribute the load. More importantly, material aged at 204°C (400°F) survived loading to 28.9 kN or 341MPa (6500 lbs. or 49.5 ksi) while material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5000 hours suffered instantaneous bearing failure at this load. At 10,000 hours, the material aged at 204°C (400°F) actually showed time dependent failure resistance superior to the unaged material by surviving 53 hours before failure at 31.1 kN or 365.4 MPa (7000lbs. or 53ksi) while unaged material only survived 38 hours.

Bearing/Bypass Interaction Test Results

The bearing/bypass interaction static tests were conducted using the 64-ply quasi-isotropic IM7/K3B specimens. Test results showed that under the tensile loading conditions, IM7/K3B specimens have higher bearing strengths both at room temperature and at elevated temperature compared to the minimum design allowable strengths. At elevated temperature 177°C (350°F), the IM7/K3B specimens under compression loadings showed significant reduction in strengths. However, compared to the required minimum allowable design bearing

Figure 7: Bearing/Bypass Static Test Results for 64-Ply IM7/K3B Laminates (Note: All Aged Specimens were Tested at RTA and UTS= Ult. Tensile Strength of Laminate)

strength at 350°F, these test values were still better. These results are shown in Fig. 7. A set of test specimens were aged for 5000 and 10000 hours at 350°F and 400°F respectively. The bearing/bypass interaction test results of these specimens have been superimposed on the bearing/bypass interaction plot, shown in Fig. 7. The aged specimens were tested only at room temperature. This was necessitated by the limited number test specimens available for testing. The test results indicate that the aging conditions used for these specimens have little or no impact on the bearing/bypass residual strength of 64-ply, quasi-isotropic IM7/K3B laminates.

CONCLUSIONS

IM7/K3B has shown itself to be insensitive to time dependent deformation. It is apparent from testing that time dependent behaviors can be expected to only show up in a very narrow band of loadings. Testing has pointed to clamp-up force as the source of the most obvious change in coupon bearing strength at temperature. Unclamped bearing testing has shown these materials can withstand their ultimate design loads at temperature, even without clamp-up force to prevent delamination.

As can be seen in the data, the material has lost bearing strength as an apparent consequence of being aged at the supersonic cruise temperature regime being explored. It should be noted that the material still withstood the ultimate design load for the joint under all tested circumstances. However, material aged at the temperature of 204°C (400°F) showed neither the same degree nor enhancement of the aging process which apparently reduced the strength of the material aged at 177°C (350°F) for 5,000 hours and 10,000 hours.

ACKNOWLEDGMENTS

This work has been supported by Lockheed Martin Aeronautical Systems under NASA HSR contract NAS1-20220 Task 24- Wing Structures. The authors extend their thanks to Mr. Ed Ingram and Mr. Brian Cornell at Lockheed Martin for their support in this effort.

REFERENCES

1. Crews, J. H., jr. and R. V. A. Naik. 1986. "Failure Analysis of a Graphite/Epoxy Laminate Subjected to Bolt Bearing Loads", *Composite Materials: Fatigue and Failure*, ASTM STP 907,; 115-133, H. T. Hahn, Ed., American Society for Testing and Materials, Philadelphia.
2. MIL-HDBK-5G. 1994. *Military Handbook: Metallic Materials and Elements for Aerospace Vehicle Structures*.
3. Sacks, S. and W. S. Johnson. 1996. "Effects of Thermal Aging on the Mechanical Behavior of K3B Matrix Material", *Proceedings of the 11th American Society for Composites Technical Conference*, Johnson, W. S. Ed. Technomic Publishing, Lancaster, Pennsylvania, 1996, pp. 666-674.